

DIALECTIC OF SOCIAL DEVELOPMENT AND EDUCATION

Kambarova Dilorom Yusupovna

Fergana State University

Associate Professor of the Department of Foreign Languages

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Annotation: Within the framework of the socialization of education in our country, the achievements of science have entered our lives, the conditions created by the state for young people in the field of science, in spite of the opportunities, among young people there is mass frivolity, meaningless life, Internet addiction, slyness, "popularity syndrome" among young people. The outbreak also requires raising the social outlook in society, changing views on life, and reevaluating the criteria for happiness.

Keywords: social, extremism and terrorism, bioterrorism, "Enlightenment and religious tolerance"

With the serious aggravation of socio-economic and political-cultural problems in the international arena, heated debates and discussions about the realization of future hopes and dreams regarding the fire of war, civil war, especially religious extremism and terrorism, bioterrorism, human rights and freedoms are escalating [1]. At the same time, it was recognized that the achievements of humanity in the field of science and technology threaten modern civilization. In a word, due to the thoughts about the rapid development of social development, the religious factor is being activated. In this sense, the stability of social development, important solutions of international and regional security, proposals and initiatives of the government of Uzbekistan regarding "Enlightenment and religious tolerance" are being scientifically analyzed by the scientists of our republic [2]. In scientific studies, scientists have recognized the harmful aspects of social development for humans, that not all changes are good, and that they have different consequences in different cultures [3].

The role of mass education is more clearly demonstrated by the conformity of political leaders and leaders to the historically formed views on the development of society and the wishes and desires of mankind. For this reason, together with the necessity of education, the formation of its popularity is widely promoted and encouraged to be enlightened so that young people can create their own destiny with their own hands on the basis of national interests. After all, social development requires deep knowledge in order for young people to take conscious and purposeful active action. In Uzbekistan, the Strategy of Actions forms universally inclusive education as a social institution and nurtures the national centuries-old spiritual heritage: scientific knowledge, skills, mastery of skills, creative thinking skills of young people. "Consequently, we need to increase our attention to human capital," says the President of Uzbekistan, "for this, we must mobilize all the possibilities" [4]. We believe that the rational use of the energy and initiative of young people will further expand the possibilities of social development, especially spiritual renaissance in Uzbekistan.

It was determined that the research of this problem in the social sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan is carried out in a number of priority directions:

- due to the implementation of the concept of "National Development and Education" under the priority of the "Social Development and Education" programs adopted by the world community, high indicators are being achieved in the general literacy of the population;

- the interrelationship of education in the development of society is recognized in foreign European countries as a legal protection of human rights and freedom, against socio-cultural discrimination;

- The essence of the state policy on youth in Uzbekistan is the compulsory primary education, the liberalization of all areas of education, the direct concern of the President of Uzbekistan to create all the conditions for education for young people, the future prospects of our country - the third Renaissance of education and training interpreted in harmony with

The Republic of Uzbekistan expressed its support for the UN Millennium Summit on Human Development on the basis of partnership. In this sense, it is emphasized that social development and education are related and development indicators are to ensure a comfortable and quality life for people [5]. These indicators and criteria represent the universal and national dialectic of social development and education in our country.

The goal of the new stage of society's development is to create a socio-economic and cultural environment for every citizen to fully demonstrate his potential under the conditions of a comfortable standard of living and healthy living conditions. In this sense, in the report of the Government of Uzbekistan to the UN on Human Development, "Education is directly related to the level of health and life expectancy of the population, that is, an important indicator of human development. Educated population takes care of their health, applies preventive measures well, lives mainly according to a healthy lifestyle, diagnoses the disease in time, provides first aid to himself, is qualified based on the fact that he turns to medical services" [6].

The President of Uzbekistan Sh.M. Mirziyoyev, relying on the national spiritual heritage to achieve social development, and on the principle that "the greatest wealth is intelligence and knowledge, the greatest heritage is good education, and the greatest poverty is ignorance", young people learn modern knowledge. The idea of mastering and becoming the owner of true enlightenment and high culture is the scientific program of our research. In particular, the declaration of Uzbekistan as the "Country of the Year" in 2019 by our president confirms the social value of education in the ongoing creative reforms [7].

In the development of the society, the socialization of the individual is the basis and structural feeling of the rational worldview, and the objective and subjective factors of educational activities and upbringing directly affect human life. In the dialectic of social development and education, a person acts as a unique indicator. Therefore, while education is an important factor of social development, the global process of social development attracts the peoples of the world to the process of advanced pedagogical technologies.

References:

1. SSHA against China // https://vsenovosty.mediasalt.ru/ssha_zateyali_podluyu_politicheskuyu_igru_protiv_kitaya (Date: 05. 08. 2021)
2. Saifnazarov I. S. Obidov A. Interreligious solidarity is a factor of social stability. - Tashkent.: Innovative Development Publishing House, 2019. -B. 5-7 (-142 p.)
3. Weber A. Issledovaniye sotsialnogo progressa: globalnogo izmereniye i vizovi dlya politiki // Vek globalizatsii. – 2016. – No. 1–2. - S. 134.

4. Mirziyoyev Sh.M. The work of a people with a great intention will be great, their life will be bright and their future will be prosperous. Volume 3. -Tashkent.: Uzbekistan. 2019. -B. 30.
5. Ensuring by the parliament of sustainable socio-economic development and implementation of the principles of human development / e.g. muh. Danilova E.K. - Tashkent.: National Development Program. 2011. – B. 4. (- 126 p.)
6. Education in Uzbekistan: supply and demand ratio. Lecture on human development / Ex. muh. G. Saidova - Tashkent.: Uzbekistan. 2008. -B. 10.
7. Mirziyoyev Sh.M. From national revival to national rise. Volume 4. - Tashkent.: Uzbekistan. 2020. -B.9

